

NOTES

Spectrophotometric Studies on the Complexes of 3-Nitroalizarin with Lanthanum, Cerium, Praseodymium, Neodymium and Samarium

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Bradford, Geyer and Smith¹ mentioned the formation of cobalt, nickel and copper complexes and described their absorption spectra in the visible range. Recently Kiel and Heertjes² prepared Ca-Al, Ca-Fe, Ca-Cr and Ca complexes of 3-nitroalizarin and established their structure by analysis and infra red spectra.

La, Ce, Pr, Nd and Sm form pink coloured complexes with 3-nitroalizarin, which are not mentioned in the existing chemical literature. The results of the spectrophotometric studies on these complexes are being presented in this communication.

Procedure: Nitroalizarin (0.07125 gm. I.C.I., England) was dissolved in 95% ethanol (250 ml.) to obtain 0.1×10^{-3} M solution. LaCl_3 , CeCl_3 , PrCl_3 , NdCl_3 , and SmCl_3 (A.B. samples chemistry Division, AEE., Bombay) were used to prepare their stock solutions in 95% ethanol. A known volume of the stock solution was evaporated to dryness, dissolved in distilled water and the rare-earth precipitated as oxalate³ and titrated with permanganate. Bausch and Lomb spectromic-20 colorimeter was employed for optical density measurements. Wave length of maximum absorbance was selected with Vosburgh and Cooper method⁴. 0.1×10^{-3} M solutions of the dye and the rare earths were mixed in the molar ratios of 1:0, 1:1, 1:2, 1:3, 2:1 and 3:1 and their optical densities were measured in the visible range. The λ_{max} was between 520 and 550 m μ for La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm complexes and 430 m μ for the pure dye respectively.

1. Bradford P. Geyer and George Mc P. Smith, *J. Amer Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 1649.

2. E. G. Kiel and P. M. Heertjes, *J. Soc. Dyers Colourists*, 1963, **79**, 186, 1963, **79**, 363.

3. James Frederick Spencer, "The Metals of the Rare-earths", Longmans Green and Co., London (1919), 103.

4. W. C. Vosburgh and G. R. Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488

The validity of Lambert and Beer's law was found in the concentration range of 0.5×10^{-4} to 0.8×10^{-4} M for these complexes.

Job's method of continued variations⁵ was performed at the corresponding wavelength maxima with 0.166×10^{-3} M, 0.125×10^{-3} M and 0.1×10^{-3} M solutions of the dye and the rare-earth salts. The difference in the optical densities of the mixtures of the dye and a rare-earth salt and of the corresponding concentration of the dye, was plotted against the composition of the mixture. The rare-earth salt solutions are colourless at such dilutions and possess no appreciable absorption. (Fig. 1).

Molar ratio method⁶ was employed to confirm the results of Job's method. 3 ml. portions of a rare-earth salt were taken in 12 test tubes and varying volumes of nitroalizarin of the same concentration were added making the total volume 15 ml. by adding re-

5. P. Job, *Compt. rend.*, 1925, 188, 928.

6. J. H. Yoc and A. L. Jones, *Eng. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.* 1944, 16, 111.

quisite amount of 95% ethanol. Corresponding concentrations of the dye were also prepared in 12 test tubes and the optical densities of both the sets measured. The difference in optical density was plotted against the volume of the dye. (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Molar Ratio Method

In another set of experiments, 6 ml. portions of the dye were taken in 12 test tubes to which varying volumes of the rare-earth salt solution added. The difference in the optical densities of these mixtures and the optical density of the constant concentration of the dye was plotted against the volume of the rare-earth salt solution (Fig. 3).

For determining the formation constant, the Job's curves were drawn with the optical density of the mixture as Y axis and the constants calculated according to the method of Banerji and Dey⁷.

Job's method yielded the molar ratio of 1 : 2 (metal: ligand) for the complexes of lanthanum, cerium, praseodymium, neodymium and samarium with 3-nitroalizarin. The

Fig. 3. Molar Ratio Method

C. No. 1.	La complex	conc.	$0.125 \times 10^{-3} M.$
C. No. 2.	Ce	"	$0.166 \times 10^{-3} M.$
C. No. 3.	Pr	"	$0.2 \times 10^{-3} M.$
C. No. 4.	Nd	"	$0.1 \times 10^{-3} M.$
C. No. 5.	Sm	"	$0.2 \times 10^{-3} M.$

log of formation constant and the free energy of formation were calculated to be of the order of 11.0 ± 0.3 and -15.0 ± 0.4 Kcals./mole respectively for these complexes.

Thanks are due to Prof. A.R. Kidwai, for providing facilities in the department and to I.C.I., England for providing the samples of the dye as a gift.